

РАЗДЕЛ. ИНФОРМАТИКА И РОБОТОТЕХНИКА

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**ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫЕ РОБОТЫ С ДВИГАТЕЛЯМИ
ПОСТОЯННОГО ТОКА, ДЕЙСТВУЮЩИЕ НА ОСНОВЕ НЕЙРО-
НЕЧЕТКОЙ ЛОГИКИ**

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Аннотация: В статье предложен вычислительный метод для построения интеллектуальной системы навигации мобильных ИК (интеллектуальных роботов). Данный метод позволяет обеспечить навигацию в нечеткой среде с динамическими и статическими препятствиями. Особенностью вычислительного метода является применение нейро-нечеткой технологии. Нейро-нечеткие технологии и мягкие вычисления являются новыми и эффективными методами построения навигации роботов и робототехнических систем. Также в статье предложена структура нейро-нечеткой системы навигации, представлены ее элементы и изложен общий принцип работы.

Ключевые слова: интеллектуальный робот, нейро-нечеткая технология, фаззификатор навигационной системы, системы визуализации и обучения

**INTELLIGENT ROBOTS WITH DC MOTORS OPERATING ON THE
BASIS OF NEURO-FUZZY LOGIC**

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Annotation: The article proposes a computational method for constructing an intelligent navigation system for mobile IR (intelligent robots). This method allows providing navigation in a fuzzy environment with dynamic and static obstacles. A feature of the computational method is the use of neuro-fuzzy technology. Neuro-fuzzy technologies and soft computing are new and effective methods for constructing navigation for robots and robotic systems. Also, the article proposes the structure of the neuro-fuzzy navigation system, presents its elements and outlines the general principle of operation.

Keywords: intelligent robot, Neuro-fuzzy technology, navigation system fuzzifier, vision and training systems

1. Introduction.

In an unknown and frequently changing dynamic environment, the IR should do the same movements as a human in a similar environment.

Recently, for designing control systems working in uncertain environment, it was considered purposeful to use new effective methods of Soft Computing technology [1-10]. Hence, for construction of navigation system with required autonomy, with the ability for reasoning and work in real time it is necessary to use the neuro-fuzzy technology, being one of the important directions of Soft Computing technology.

Therefore, an intelligent system for navigation of an IR in an uncertain and dynamic environment can most effectively be created on the basis of combination of the two modern technologies-fuzzy logic and Neuro-Computing.

2. Features of the problem of navigation.

Neuro-fuzzy technology is used to implement the Meta operators.

Methods of Soft Computing are based on computing methods which can work with fuzzy and uncertain information and enables finding a purposeful solution with less cost. It is known that various kinds of fuzzy control are realized on the basis of rules in linguistic form [5].

The various variants of inferences are suggested in the literature [7].

Type 1: Applying function MIN for estimations of precise input, the degree of accomplishment of conditional part of rule is calculated as

$$M_i = \mu_{A_1k_1}(x_1)\mu_{A_2k_2}(x_2) \dots \mu_{A_mk_m}(x_m) = \prod_{j=1}^m \mu_{A_jk_j}(x_j)$$

Then the output of the right part of rule and procedure of defuzzification is performed:

$$y_1 = \frac{M_1B_{11} + M_2B_{21} + \dots + M_rB_{r1}}{\sum_{i=1}^r M_i}$$

Here: $B_{ii} = \mu_{B_{ii}}^{-1}(y_1)$.

Type 2: In this case monotony of membership function for estimations of fuzzy output is required. In this connection the procedure of defuzzification is complicated and described by formula (1).

$$B_{i1} = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left\{ \left(1 - \prod_i \left(\mu_{B_{is1i}}(y_1) \right) \right) y_1 \right\} dy_1}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left\{ \left(1 - \prod_i \left(\mu_{B_{is1i}}(y_1) \right) \right) \right\} dy_1}. \quad (1)$$

Type 3: Method of Takagi-Sugeno.

Because of a set of fuzzy rules, participated in decision-making process, the computing a conditional output will be very reliable and stable against noise.

For the functional optimization of quality of empirical adjustment of knowledge base, some changes in the conclusions of experiments are required.

For the solution of the navigation problem of the intelligent robot the application of Neuro-fuzzy system is necessary to take into account the following ideas. The environment of the robot is uncertain and dynamic and the environment includes set of objects changing their sizes and states. And consequently in case of missing the knowledge about the environment the control and decision-making is possible on the basis of information from the vision system only. This system can provide only limited information of the environment. Despite of this the camera system is used for finding the safe distance up to an obstacle in a way to the goal.

For collision-free movements in the dynamic environment the control system should periodically address to the vision system. Speed of the moving is adjusted dependent on change of the state of the environment and speed of the robot.

Movement of the robot is initiated by commands coming to the servomotor from the control system and these commands determine movement of the robot to the left, to the right, forward and stopping the robot.

3. Architecture of the control system/

The architecture of the control system providing purposeful behavior of IR, working in a complex dynamic environment characterized by uncertainty (fig. 1), is suggested in work [6].

At the first level of architecture of IR control system, the basic function of the scheduler consists of the automatic decision to move intelligent robot on the basis of the corresponding data and knowledge.

Direct behavior of IR is realized as the part of the subsystem of navigation, taking place on II level. The control system at this stage formalizes control commands on the basis of a trajectory of the plan found at the first level and knowledge of reflex activity kept in the knowledge base, the current situation of the visual information and fuzzy coordinates of IR. The sequence of these commands provides realization of the plan. Commands transform to effectors signals, passing through subsystems at third (III) level.

Figure 1 – The architecture of the fuzzy control system for intelligent robot

Creating the system of planning and navigation of IR, it is necessary to take into account, that the environment of actions of these robots is uncertain, dynamic, partially or not-structured. The IR should understand the structure of the environment, create a trajectory of optimum transition from any location to the one by creating a map of environment on the basis of development of the uncertain sensor information and perceiving both static and dynamic obstacles on its way and should move on the basis of this trajectory. In this case the scheduler of IR, should create sequence of operators (in initially uncertain environment) providing movement of the robot from a point B to the point C.

Generated operators are executed by navigation system of IR. It is assumed that IR is equipped with devices of orientation and technical vision. At this level input parameters of IR are visual information and its current parameters. The purpose of navigation system of IR is in on-line mode, during short time under the given plan to move the IR from a point B to a point C, avoiding both static and dynamic obstacles.

In general as a whole the control of IR is reduced to the planning of its purposeful movement, to navigation and to adaptive stabilization. In a chain of these hierarchical problems the solution of latter problem takes into account such synthesis of algorithm of adaptive control that they could get into the reality planned trajectory of IR in the uncertain environment.

General structure of control system of IR is shown in figure 2. The structure of the control system consists of the following blocks:

1. Vision system (VS).
2. The device for calculation of direction to goal (DCDG).
3. Distance fuzzifiers (F).
4. The block for control formalizing control commands (BFCC).
5. System of training (ST).
6. The DC motor of the Robot (DM).

DCDG can do an estimation of the goal in different ways.

On the basis of the information transmitted to it (robot coordinate system and current coordinates of the goal).

It receives a signal from the goal (a sound or an electromagnetic signal) and determines the relation to the goal, knowing the direction of this signal.

Request the direction to the goal from the operator.

DCDG receives signal, BFCC creates a control command, and this command is sent directly to the servomotor of the robot. Fuzzifiers are determining the relation between fuzzy input variables and control commands used in rules.

Figure 2 – General structure of the navigation system of mobile robot

In this case the input fuzzifier evaluates distance up to an obstacle measured by sensor or received from the vision system. Thus, the number of fuzzifiers is the same as the number of input estimations used for the environment of the robot. If in front of the robot there is no obstacle the signal from the fuzzifier is equal to zero. If there is an obstacle BFCC will modify the moving of the robot such that it avoid the obstacle still keeping the direction to the goal. The second (hidden) layer of neurons in neural network of BFCC shows fuzzy rules, number of neurons shows number of rules. In classical fuzzy mechanism of extraction the output neurons is processed by function MIN (AND). In algorithm of training this function is replaced by other function, allowing mathematical processing.

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